

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY OF A FRONT FACING CAPTURE CHAMBER

Michael E. McCormick and Joseph C. Canvin

Naval Systems Engineering Department
U. S. Naval Academy
Annapolis, Maryland 21402-5042

ABSTRACT

Experimental results on a two-dimensional oscillating water column capture chamber show that the ideal chamber length to wavelength ratio value of 0.25 is not actually ideal. The results further show that the operational design of an oscillating water column prototype is best done for a swell condition. Finally, the capture chamber length must be small enough to prevent internal traveling waves.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most of us working in the various areas of ocean technology are aware of the recent efforts in converting the energy of ocean waves into more usable forms. The two products resulting from wave energy conversion that first come to mind are electricity and potable water. Masuda [1] discusses the former, while Hicks [2] discusses the latter.

After a decade or so of moderate interest in wave energy conversion including an at-sea prototype study on the floating platform "Kaimei" (see Masuda [3]) a large-scale commercial venture has been initiated by the Norwegians, as described by Berge [4]. That project involves a pneumatic wave energy conversion system similar to that sketched in Figure 1, and utilizes a modified Wells Turbine (see Whittaker [5]). The turbine (poorly sketched in Figure 1 is a counter-rotating McCormick turbine (see Masuda [3]) which was used on the Kaimei along with the Wells turbine and other turbines contributed by both Japan and Great Britain.

The question is often asked as to how long the capture chamber should be (L in Figures 1 and 2) for optimal performance of a pneumatic system. Theoretically, the length should be one-quarter of the wavelength (λ), as predicted by McCormick [6] and others. As most engineers know, there are occasional differences between theoretical and actual performance. Hence, in the present study we attempt to experimentally determine the optimum capture chamber length using the system sketched in Figure 2.

The equations used in the data reduction can be found in the books of McCormick [7], Newman [8] and others.

2. EXPERIMENT

The experimental study described herein was conducted in the 120-foot (36.6-meter) wave and towing tank of the U.S. Naval Academy's Hydromechanics Laboratory. The tank is 8 feet (2.44 meters) in width and had a water depth of 5 feet (1.52 meters) for the study.

Referring to Figure 2, the capture chamber was made of reinforced Plexiglass sheeting so that a video tape could be made of the internal free-surface motions. The top of the chamber straddled the tank and was supported by the tank walls. The front lip of the chamber extended down 2.10 feet (0.641 meter) from the top and 1.15 feet (0.351 meter) into the water. Hence, the height of the air chamber above the still water level was 0.950 foot (0.290 meter). A hole of 0.25 foot (0.0762 meter) diameter was located 1 foot (0.305 meter) from the front of the chamber. The hole was, then, a sharp-edged orifice having a 0.0417-foot (0.0127 meter) thickness. Since the effect of the chamber length (L in Figures 1 and 2) was of special interest, the back wall of the chamber was positioned at five different locations during the study. Values of L for these locations were 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10 feet (0.61, 1.22, 1.83, 2.44 and 3.05 meters).

The incident wave properties were measured with resistance wave gauges respectively positioned 12.7 feet (3.87 meters) and 36.9 feet (11.3 meters) from the chamber mouth. A sonic probe was located at the center of the chamber for each chamber length, although it was more accurate to

visually determine the internal wave height since the nature of the internal waves changed. That is, for some frequencies standing waves were present, while for others internal traveling waves occurred. A pressure gauge was also located in the air chamber below the orifice. The gauge was positioned 0.475 foot (0.145 meter) above the still water level. Air velocity measurements were made with a probe placed above the center of the orifice. Thus, only the spacially maximum velocities were measured for each wave frequency.

The wave frequency range studied was from 0.30 Hz to 1.00 Hz. For the 5.00 foot (1.52-meter) depth, then, the nature of the waves varied from intermediate water to deep water. The corresponding wavelengths, determined from

$$\lambda = (g/2\pi f^2) \text{ tank } (2\pi h/\lambda) \quad (1)$$

ranged from 38.4 feet (11.7 meters) down to 5.12 feet (1.56 meters). In equation (1), g is the gravitational constant (32.2 ft/s^2 or 9.81 m/s^2) f is the frequency in Hz and h is the water depth. The incident wave heights (H) varied from 0.250 feet (0.0762 meter) to 0.392 feet (0.119 meter).

3. RESULTS

The orifice hole is the primary energy extraction device in the system sketched in Figure 2. The energy balance for the entire system is mathematically represented by

$$E = E_r + E_o + E_v + E_p + E_w \quad (2)$$

where

E = incident wave energy

E_r = radiated plus reflected wave energies

E_o = energy extracted by the orifice

E_v = energy lost due to viscosity and other irrotationalities

E_p = energy stored by the pressurized air in the chamber

E_w = energy of the internal wave

Because of the difficulty in determining all of these energies, we have chosen to study the system performance by comparing the time-average air power through the orifice (P_o) and the averaged incident wave power (P), the latter determined from

$$P = \rho g H^2 C_g B/8 \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the mass-density of the fresh water in the tank (1.93 slugs/ft^3 or $1,000 \text{ kg/m}^3$), C_g is the groups velocity obtained from

$$C_g = \frac{\lambda f}{2} \left[1 + \frac{4\pi\lambda/h}{\sinh(4\pi\lambda/h)} \right] \quad (4)$$

and B is the tank width (8.00 feet or 2.44 meters). Since all the wave conditions of interest are nearly sinusoidal, the air velocity at the center of the orifice can be expressed by

$$V = V_o \cos(2\pi ft) \quad (5)$$

and the internal air pressure by

$$p = p_o \sin(2\pi ft) \quad (6)$$

Hence, the time-averaged power of the air passing through the hole of area A is

$$\begin{aligned} P_o &= 4Af \int_0^{1/4f} pV dt \\ &= p_o V_o A/4 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

An "efficiency" of the energy extraction can now be written in terms of the relationships of equations (3) and (7) as

$$\begin{aligned} E &= P_o/P \\ &= 8 p_o V_o A/\rho g H^2 C_g B\pi \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Experimental values of E are presented in Figures 3 and 4 as functions of L/λ . In Figure 3, a semi-log plot is presented so that all the experimental results can be seen. For $0 < L/\lambda < 0.6$ traveling waves occur. In Figure 4 the data are shown for the range of $0 < L/\lambda < 0.6$ in decimal form. The reader can see that at values of $L/\lambda \approx 0.25$ relative peaks occur in several of the data plots ($L = 2$ and 8 feet). The data points on either side of the 0.25 value are approximately the same for $L = 4$ feet, while the $L = 10$ feet data begin at $L/\lambda = 0.260$. The E values that are greater than one do not represent an actual "efficiency" greater than unity. As is explained in the next section, these high values of E are simply due to the non-spacially averaged air velocity values in the orifice. That is, the maximum value at the center is assumed to be uniform over the orifice area, which is far from actuality.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the study, a two-dimensional front-facing oscillating water column system is subjected to a series of nearly linear (sinusoidal) waves. The performance of the system is determined from plots of a quasi-efficiency [E in equation (8)] as a function of chamberlength to wavelength ratio in Figures 3 and 4. There are five sets of data corresponding to five values of the capture chamber length, L .

First of all, the dimensionless groupings in Figures 4 and 5 are evidently not ideal since the data do not close. That is, the data do not converge to a single line (with some expected scatter). For the purpose of this study, however, the variable L/λ is correct in that we are investigating the performance in the neighborhood

of the ideal value of 0.25. The air power used in the power ratio E is idealized in that the assumption is made that the maximum velocity is uniform over the hole. In fact, the velocity profiles resemble those sketched in Figure 5. One can see the large source error. The magnitude of the error depends on both the magnitude and condition (laminar or turbulent) of the air flow, both of which are frequency and capture chamber length dependent.

The high values of E at the lower L/λ values indicate that the best performance of a prototype would be in a swell condition rather than a wind-wave condition. This result is good for the designer since the swells are more consistent in most locations.

One of the main goals in the design of oscillating water columns in resonance. That is, the designer would like to have the average wave frequency the same as the natural frequency of the water column. Neglecting the effects of air compressibility, the natural frequency of system is determined from

$$f_n = (1/2\pi) \sqrt{g/(m + m^1)} \quad (9)$$

where m is the mass of water given by

$$m = \rho d BL \quad (10)$$

and m¹ is the added mass. Using equation (9) with m¹ = 0, the natural frequency range for 2 < L < 10 feet is 0.152 > f_n > 0.0678 Hz. The effect of the inclusion of the added mass in equation (9) would be to lower the frequency range and, consequently the L/λ range. This means that resonance with the swell (our desired wave) is possible with the proper choice of L.

The high values of L/λ, i.e., greater than 0.6, correspond to the high frequency traveling waves within the chamber. These waves have little extractable power associated with them, as evidenced by the results in Figure 3. They do, however, cause problems by reflecting off of the lip and back walls. In a prototype capture chamber these internal traveling waves could cause structural damage.

We conclude the following:

1. The theoretical ideal relationship between L and λ (L/λ = 0.25) is not actually ideal.
2. A design goal should be operation in a swell, either at or near resonance.
3. The chamber length should be kept as small as possible so as to avoid higher frequency internal traveling waves.

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FIGURE 1. Sketch of a Front-Facing Pneumatic Wave Energy Converter.

FIGURE 2. Sketch of the Experimental Set-Up.

FIGURE 3. Power Ratio as a Function of Chamber-Length-to-Wavelength Ratio.

FIGURE 4. Power Ratio as a Function of Chamber-Length-to-Wavelength Ratio for Internal Standing Waves Only.

FIGURE 5. Velocity Profiles Over First Half-Period.